

RELEVANCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL INFLUENCES FOR LAMB WAVE BASED SHM WITH PIEZOELECTRIC ELEMENTS

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Keywords: *Lamb Wave, SHM, Environmental Influences, compensation, CFRP*

1 Introduction

During recent years, Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) has seen increasing attention of the research community due to its potential to increase safety while at the same time decreasing maintenance costs and structural weight. One main research focus, due to the importance of the economical and ecological effects of these improvements, is the application of SHM for aeronautical structures. With their complex geometry, anisotropic materials and the wide range of possible environmental effects and load states, coupled with safety concerns and a high cost pressure, these structures are a challenging environment for the successful integration of SHM technologies.

One of the possible SHM methods that seem well-suited for the task is the use of so called Lamb waves, a type of guided plate waves first described by H. LAMB in the early 20th century. These waves have a range of interesting properties making them apparently ideal for the monitoring of large structures: they propagate in two dimensions, allowing for sparse sensor arrays, are easily excited and measured in a way suitable for SHM (using, for example, integrated or surface-applied piezoelectric elements) and, most importantly, are highly sensitive for most types of damage encountered in composite aerospace structures. During recent years, they have successfully been used to identify and localize both various discrete, localized damages, such as holes, notches, cracks, delaminations or debonding [1-3], as well as distributed, non-localized damage such as fatigue in composites [4]. Examples for other applications are the measurement of humidity absorption [5] or the inverse measurement of mechanical properties [6].

Due to their proven ability to detect damage, the research attention has shifted more towards

accommodating the requirements faced in real applications: damage identification and compensation schemes. Both the ability to confidently identify a certain type and/or level of damage and the ability to reliably distinguish between damage-related signal changes and those resulting from changes of the state of structure and monitoring system are prerequisites for any out-of-laboratory use of Lamb wave based SHM.

Recent work in this areas has focused on wave behavior and damage identification in more and more complex structures [7-9], where their multi-modal nature, reflections and mode conversion increase the signals complexity, and on compensation methods to account for signal changes due to environmental effects. The most common and virtually unavoidable factor is temperature, which has therefore been at the center of various research activities [10-13]. Other factors include local liquid pooling on the structures surface [14] or humidity absorption, which is a larger issue for composite materials due to the commonly used polymeric matrices [15].

Much of the work performed was focused on metallic, isotropic structures, which are still by far the most commonly used materials for structural parts in the aerospace industry. However, a rising amount of parts is made from anisotropic composite parts, which leads to various changes in both Lamb wave behavior and the alterations due to environmental effects. In this work, the most important influences on active Lamb wave based SHM of composite structures that are unrelated to damage are presented and their impact on composite-specific SHM and two compensation strategies is discussed.

2 Environmental Influences on Lamb Wave Based SHM with Active Piezoelectric Elements

The principle of Lamb wave based SHM with active piezoelectric elements is simple (Fig. 1): a permanently integrated or attached piezoelectric element acts as an actuator (2), the generated Lamb wave propagates through the structure that is to be monitored (5), and a second piezoelectric element is used to measure the arriving wave (pitch-catch, 8) or the actuator measures reflections coming back from local stiffness changes or damage.

Fig. 1: Principle of active Lamb wave based SHM [15]

Changes of the signal imply changes of either parts of the SHM system or the structure between them and could therefore indicate damage. In this chapter, the system used for experimental measurements and its parts sensitive to environmental changes are described. Afterwards, common methods for damage detection and their reliance on certain signal features are described, before, in 2.3, experimental results for various common influences on Lamb wave propagation in composite materials are shown and compared.

2.1 SHM System and Set-Up

All experimental work was performed using a system similar to that shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Experimental set-up

A 3-cycle Hann-windowed sinusoidal burst was used for actuation, generated by an HP 33120A signal generator and amplified using a Krohn-Hite 7602 wideband amplifier. Two types of actuators/sensors and specimen were used. For load-free measurements (temperature and humidity changes and combinations thereof), round PZT discs (diameter 10mm, thickness 0.2mm) were bonded to the surface of carbon composite plates (500x500 mm²) using Z70 adhesive. For measurements featuring quasi-static and/or fatigue loading, rectangular specimen with a length of 500 mm and a width of 20 mm were used in combination with rectangular PZT sensors (30x5x0.2 mm³). Specimen made from RTM6 resin and G1157 reinforcement fabrics featuring various layups and thicknesses were tested. To minimize reflections, the ends of the rectangular specimen and the edges of the plate specimen were covered with a sealing mass. The sensor responses were measured at varying frequencies using a TDS 3014B oscilloscope and the averages of 128 measurements. Temperature and humidity were controlled using a Vötsch VC0018 environmental chamber. Quasi-static loads were applied using a Zwick/Roell Z250 while an MTS 370 was used for fatigue tests. The test specimen were subjected entirely to the various influences, resulting in changes not only to the material itself and therefore wave propagation (5 in Fig. 2) and damping (6), but also to the sensors/actuators (2), the adhesive layer (3), and the coupling between the piezoelectric elements and the structure (4). Therefore, a compensation approach has to include changes to the signal resulting from changes of the SHM system itself.

2.2 Influences on the Signal and their Relevance for Damage Detection

SOHN et al. define damage as "[...] changes introduced into a system that adversely affect its current or future performance" [16]. Conversely, anything that changes the system without adversely affecting its performance is no damage, and an SHM system should therefore compensate the effect such changes have on the signal used for damage detection to avoid false output. This makes signal changes related to the intended use of the structure, e.g. strain from loads, an obvious influence on an SHM system. While such influences by themselves

could, in theory, be accounted for by performing SHM in a known state (e.g. pre-flight), environmental factors exist which can both alter the Lamb wave behavior by themselves and the state of the structure in a defined, unchanged load situation. These factors become relevant when, after compensation, the remaining signal change is indistinguishable from damage or rather the influence of a possible damage scenario on the feature used for damage identification. As an example, CLARKE et al. specify a value of -40 dB between the signal amplitude and remaining non-damage related changes after compensation for an open sensor network in a metallic structure as desirable [10].

Going through Fig. 1 from actuation to measurement, one can see that (assuming that the electronic devices and the connection to and from the piezoelectric elements do not change) the input voltage (1) is first converted to a mechanical strain (2), then transferred through a shear layer (3) into the coupled structure with the shear layers own properties, the properties of the sensor and the structure itself (and therefore, in a composite material, the orientation) and the way they interact (4) influencing the actuated wave(s). These waves then propagate through the structure (5) in a dispersive, mode dependent manner while being damped both internally (6) and possibly externally (7). Additionally, the waves will interact with any kind of disturbance that alters the stiffness, both structural and due to damage, by (possibly) being reflected, refracted, transmitted and converted into other modes. At the sensor (8) the process of actuation is reversed, with the surface strain being transferred through the coupling agent into the sensor. The sensor then converts the sum of strains into a measurable electrical voltage. From these processes, a set of properties can be found which influences the measured signal and whose changes, if created due to non-damaging influences, have to be compensated. Apart from geometric features (sensor size and thickness, adhesive layer thickness etc.), these are:

- Mechanical and electrical properties of actuator and sensor
- Mechanical properties of the coupling agent/adhesive
- Mechanical properties of the waveguide.

If one looks at an actual flight cycle, than the most obvious influences are loads and temperature changes. Many possible ways to account for these have been researched. Approaches include the use a database of known acceptable responses at all possible states (optimal baseline selection – OBS) or the correct compensation of changes to a single baseline, e.g. by stretching it in time (baseline signal stretch – BSS) or shifting it (local temporal coherence). Other methods include approaches comparing changes of multiple propagation paths (esp. if there is a multitude of paths, as in Lamb wave tomography) and using baseline-free approaches such as time reversal [1].

Many of these approaches, while still working to some extent, have to be adapted to deal with some of the composite-specific changes to the monitored system. Firstly, changes to a fiber reinforced composite structure will lead to more mode-dependent changes than in isotropic materials. With the actuation, propagation, damping and measurement of each Lamb wave mode depending in varying amounts on different parts of the materials anisotropic stiffness tensor, varying changes to the material lead to different reactions for different modes (and at different frequencies, due to the varying composition of the wave modes from shear and longitudinal movement). Additionally, the changes will be direction-dependent.

Secondly, there are non-damage related changes in composite materials that happen slowly (ageing, absorption processes and fatigue cracks in the matrix, also these might be seen as damage, depending on the design philosophy). This leads to unknown undamaged states due to the inability to obtain measurements in every possible state, esp. if one additionally considers the large variation of such factors over the materials thickness (e.g. quick humidity intake close to the surface or temperature gradient over thickness when inner and outer temperature differ).

Thirdly the nature of the piezoelectric measurement devices used is integrative, measuring the strain over its whole body. That means it is not always possible (with a single sensor) to discern between overlapping waves as they interfere in the signal, meaning that in certain configurations (e.g. for certain material parameters/frequencies, for small propagation distances or close to / disadvantageously positioned relative to a stiffness

discontinuity), interfering waves will exist at the position of the sensor, and these will behave differently (e.g. show different relative velocity changes) due to the aforementioned factors, leading to changing interference patterns.

Lastly, the material damping of most composite materials is far higher than that of commonly used metals such as aluminum and steel. As the influence of the stiffness on wave propagation, this damping is mode-dependent and direction-dependent even for composite materials showing in-plane isotropy, making it more complicated to account for than in isotropic cases.

In summary, Lamb waves in composite materials exhibit mode- and orientation-dependent behavior (actuation, propagation, damping and measurement) and, most important for compensation, influences on any part of the system also depend on mode and orientation. Additionally, factors exist which cannot be accounted for by unmodified prerecorded baselines due to their slow nature. These changes additionally might vary locally (e.g. higher humidity in the bilge area) or depending on the structure (especially if said structure is complex, e.g. contains thickness variations).

While all these effects do exist, their relevance for real compensation methods depends on the magnitude (and type) of change they evoke in the signal and the dependence of the compensation scheme on the signal feature changed. The following chapter therefore presents some common factors influence on typical signal features to underline their relevance.

2.3 Effects of Environmental Influences on Lamb Wave Behavior

The most common factors which influence the Lamb waves mentioned before were load and temperature changes. Both were topic of a lot of recent research [4, 9-12] and are shown here mainly to emphasize some of the composite specific effects and to obtain a relative comparison to factors uncommon to metal. These factors are humidity absorption and fatigue as well as their interaction with the aforementioned ones. Some selected examples illustrating the influence of these factors on wave excitation, propagation, damping and measurement are shown

on the following pages and the changes specific to composite materials are highlighted.

The data obtained from the experiments described in chapter 2.1 yields, after common preparation routines have been performed (averaging, smoothing, CWT-filtering and Hilbert transformation) the measured amplitudes, velocities and damping coefficients of the lowest two wave modes S_0 and A_0 over an experiment-specific frequency range. Fig. 3 displays an example of this set of results for waves propagating in a cross-ply reinforced plate (layup: $[0_2/90_2]_s$, propagation direction: 45° , thickness: $\sim 2\text{mm}$, production process: MVI).

Fig. 3: Measured amplitudes (200 mm distance from actuator), damping coefficients and velocities (measured between 200 mm and 320 mm) in 45° -direction in a 2 mm cross-ply carbon reinforced plate.

From multiple of these result sets, obtained at different temperatures and after different conditioning periods (conditioning at $70^\circ\text{C}/90\%$ humidity saturation), the relative changes displayed in Fig. 4 were obtained. These Figures illustrate the influence of temperature changes and humidity absorption as well as their combination on the lower Lamb wave modes. The significant impact both temperature changes and humidity absorption have on Lamb wave propagation is easily visible. Additionally, the comparable magnitude of the influence of both factors underlines the need for humidity absorption compensation in fiber reinforced plastics.

Fig. 4: Left: relative changes of the S_0 -modes amplitudes due to temperature changes and hot/wet-conditioning, right: absolute differences between the measured damping coefficients due to hot/wet-conditioning and temperature changes for two perpendicular propagation paths. Both measurements taken in a cross-ply reinforced plate, layup $[90_2/0_2]_s$, orientation (left), and as given in the legend (right), distance to actuator of the first sensor ~ 200 mm and of the second sensor (for damping measurement) ~ 300 mm.

The most obvious conclusion from Fig. 4 is that both the excited amplitude and the damping coefficient depend on the propagation orientation, even in a cross-ply reinforced material. Changes due to temperature and humidity absorption are similar in magnitude, meaning that humidity absorption can not be disregarded. Additionally, the significant mode dependency of the changes to the Lamb waves, even when propagating along the same axis, is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Top: mode-dependent lag between the baseline (taken at room temperature) and its optimal fit from an in situ signal taken at 70°C , bottom: baseline and in situ signal over time.

The time lag between a windowed part of the baseline and its best fitting counterpart in the in situ signal is small for the S_0 -Mode, arriving first, before it jumps to a higher value for the second (A_0) mode due to the higher sensitivity of the second one to changes of the out of plane properties, which are more significantly altered by temperature changes than the in plane properties in fiber direction.

For a compact presentation of the principal significance of various kinds of influences on Lamb wave excitation, propagation and measurement, the impact of these changes on the excited amplitudes of the lowest two modes was evaluated using the following equation:

$$R = A_{A0}(f_{A0}, I_x) / A_{S0}(f_{S0}, I_x) / (A_{A0}(f_{A0}, 0) / A_{S0}(f_{S0}, 0)). \quad (1)$$

A are amplitudes measured at a fixed distance, f is a fixed frequency and I_x is a value representing a certain influence, e.g. days under hot/wet-conditions or load level applied. If $f_{A0} = f_{S0}$ and a change in R occurs, then the sum of I_x s impact on the SHM system and the structure under surveillance is mode-dependent, a fact which would have to be compensated for.

Fig. 6: Changes of the amplitude ratio between A_0 - and S_0 -mode due to various factors. All results for waves propagating in a cross-ply carbon fiber reinforced plate, layup $[0_2/90_2]$, propagation in 0° -direction. Temperatures are given in $^\circ\text{C}$, the loading level in microstrain (ue) and the number of fatigue cycles in kilocycles.

For a set of different I_x , the experimental results are shown in Fig. 6. The measurement frequencies f_{A_0} and f_{S_0} were chosen to be 75 kHz for all experiments using plates and round sensors (first four groups in Fig. 6) and 39 kHz for all experiments using rectangular sensors and thin specimen to obtain A_0 - and S_0 -amplitudes of similar magnitude at $I_x=0$.

From Fig. 6, some interesting results are visible. Firstly, all factors mentioned in 2.2 have at least a minimal influence on the results. Additionally, even the factor found to be most insignificant in Fig. 6 (number of fatigue cycles) underlines this: in this case, the influence is low because 0° -layers show little property degradation in fiber direction. At the measurement frequency, S_0 is dominated by these layers due to their large contribution to the stiffness in the direction of propagation, while A_0 is dominated by their stiffness due to their large contribution to the bending properties. For specimen with a propagation direction in 90° , the influence was found to be much higher.

Secondly, the mode dependency of all changes and, additionally, the large importance of slow factors like humidity absorption is obvious. The first group, showing the impact of hot/wet-conditioning over

time, is a good example for this: first, a quick, large drop of the relative ratio is observed. Its reason is the quick humidity absorption of the outmost layers and the adhesive couplant. Afterwards, a slow increase can be monitored. This is due to the slower absorption of humidity and the accompanying higher damping and lower stiffness. S_0 , being similar to a pressure wave at these frequencies, is influenced more pronouncedly by these changes than A_0 , which behaves more like a bending wave and is therefore influenced more by the properties of the outer layers. Thirdly, the influence of multiple superposed factors can be seen. A very good example is the reversal of the behavior due to changing temperatures before and after hot/wet conditioning (groups 3 and 4 in Fig. 6).

In addition to the active measurements described before, passive measurements of the sensor responses to a known impact excitation were performed. For this, an impact hammer was repeatedly used on a unidirectionally reinforced plate (layup: $[0_{12}]$) in a known position. The plate was then h/w-conditioned and the measurements repeated at room temperature in regular intervals. The changes of the sensor responses are shown in

Fig. 7 and display, just as the changes of the active measurements, a clearly visible dependency on the direction. The magnitude for the changes is large for all directions, also resin-dominated directions display the biggest drop in signal amplitude due to the higher relative property changes during humidity absorption.

Fig. 7: Changes of the sensor response of a passive SHM system (normalized using the maximal contact force) due to 35 days of hot/wet-conditioning.

It is important to stress the fact that the changes in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 do not document the influence of the factors on the material or the Lamb wave propagation alone. They rather shows the accumulated impact of the influences on the entire structure and SHM system, and therefore potentially include effects such as sensor degradation. An example is the result obtained for static loading equivalent to 0,3 % strain, which lead to the formation of visible cracks in the sensor and the large jump in results shown in group 5 in Fig. 6. It is additionally important to emphasize that such measurements, while less adequate for an investigation of the Lamb waves behavior alone, are of utmost importance for practical applications. The factors investigated are not atypical for tests that structural composite parts have to pass resp. requirements they have to fulfill, meaning that an integrated SHM system will necessarily have to be able to survive such conditions, too.

3. Compensation

For an influencing factor on Lamb wave propagation in composites with significant impact on relevant signal features to be compensatable, a set of requirements have to be fulfilled by the compensation scheme:

- No reliance on prior knowledge of the response change due to non-damaging factors (slow processes such as humidity absorption make this unfeasible)
- Confined to one narrowband mode at a time (e.g. windowed in time, necessary due to mode and direction dependency in composites, which leads to time-dependent relative signal changes)
- As little interference as possible, at least within the first arriving wave package (due to the inability to separate the single wave packages contribution to the signal and the package-specific signal changes)
- Partly based on amplitude (non-interfering packages = low amplitude regions in time, characterized by a low SNR)

It is obvious from these points that certain combinations of part geometry and sensor placement with certain influencing effects can lead to uncompensatable effects. An example would be a sensor placed so close to a reflecting stiffness discontinuity that reflection and direct signal overlap. Uncompensatable, in this instance, does not mean that it is downright impossible to compensate for these factors, it just means that compensating for them would require an unrealistically high amount of costs, time and/or effort. For the given example, OBS would work, however the amount of time required to reach all possible saturation states (esp. if the possible thickness variation of humidity saturation is accounted for) is prohibitive. In this chapter, two exemplary compensation methods are briefly described and typical results are depicted. The limitations of both approaches and the reasons behind them are then discussed.

3.1 Two Compensation Approaches

Two compensation methods, one for active (wave actuated by a dedicated piezoelement) and one for passive (wave actuated by impact event) SHM, where applied to data gathered from specimen under various conditions and with added discrete damage.

The first one was based on the local temporal coherence method (see [17]), which uses the peak coherence and the time delay between windowed

parts of a baseline signal and an in situ signal to identify damage. For sufficiently large, undisturbed structures and short signals, it fulfills the

Fig. 8: A: Local Temporal Coherence between a baseline signal and a signal taken from a UD-reinforced plate after cutting a hole with $r=15$ mm (offside the propagation path) over frequency and window n (window length = 150% T), B: Relative mean square error (RMSE) between baseline and its reconstruction from the in situ signal for the same case, C: RMSE after 3 days of hot/wet-conditioning, D: RMSE of an undamaged plate after temperature increase to 45 °C, E: RMSE of the same plate after 36 days of hot/wet-conditioning at room temperature and F: RMSE measured on a plate with a single stiffener positioned between actuator and sensor.

aforementioned requirements except for the last one, and can easily be expanded by either using the normalized residual sum of squares between the baseline and the baseline reconstruction from the in situ signal using the moment of peak coherence or discharging all values from windows below a certain amplitude in both baseline and in situ signal. The best possible fit is created by finding the part of the in situ signal with the highest coherence when compared to the baseline, shifting it using the time lag of the peak coherence and scaling it using the quotient between the cross-correlation of both windowed signals and the autocorrelation of the in situ signal. The resulting signal is a reconstruction of the baseline using the in situ signal and can be used to evaluate, e.g., the mean square error between the baseline and its fit. This can be normalized using, e.g., the largest RMS of the windowed baseline, which has the advantage that areas containing little energy are easier to identify than from pure coherence plots (see Fig. 8 A and B). Fig. 8 B shows the general ability of such an approach to detect damage via the inability to reconstruct the baseline from the in situ signal.

The second method, compensation for a passive approach, reconstructs the impact force by first using a simple plate model of the structure (similar to [18]) and then inversely calculating all necessary material parameters from additional active measurements. For this, the material properties are obtained using an algorithm similar to [19], the factor between surface strain and output voltage is calculated using a calibration loop before actual use, and the environmental impact on the SHM system itself is accounted for by comparing the measured drop of the excited amplitudes for a known configuration during active measurements with the measured rise of the damping coefficients (with changes not explainable by the material property changes necessarily being a product of changes to the SHM system itself). More information can be found in [20].

The results of this adaptive compensation method are displayed in Fig. 9. The same unidirectionally reinforced plate that was used to obtain the results in Fig. 7 (CFRP, 12 layers of G1157 and RTM 6 resin) was used in this experiments, with the values shown in Fig. 9 calculated using 3 sensors distributed around the point of impact in varying directions. Both the significant influence of conditioning on

contact force reconstruction and an improvement of the reconstructed force maximum are visible.

Fig. 9: Reconstructed maximal contact force with and without compensation during hot/wet-conditioning.

3.2 Constraints and Limitations of the Approaches

While both methods shown in 3.1 are in principle able to compensate changes unrelated to damage, various effects can lead to an inability for both to fulfill their role. For the first method, which basically evaluates changes of the in situ signals coherence with the baseline, the most important point is the compliance with all points mentioned in chapter 3. However, two of these points are not always accomplishable, which leads to the large changes unrelated to damage that are shown in Fig. 8: the confinement to one narrowband mode at a time and the nonexistence of interfering modes. The first point is hampered by the fact that a short signal is desirable if little interferences are aspired to, but that a short signal has a broader frequency content. In combination with the dispersive propagation and damping of the waves, this will lead to changes of the signal shape. The importance of these points is visible in Fig. 8 C and D: even in an undamaged state, the similarity between two signals will drop due to factors such as temperature changes or humidity absorption, leading to large differences between the baseline and its reconstruction from in situ data. Even more important, these changes can be larger than those resulting from actual damage, which is clearly visible when comparing Fig. 8 B (change due to damage) and C (change due to 3 days of hot/wet-conditioning).

The second point, no interferences, is problematic in a complex structure (such as Fig. 10) due to the existence of local stiffness discontinuities in an undamaged state.

Fig. 10: Skin with omega stringer reinforcements acting as discontinuities.

Such discontinuities are a source for reflections, refraction and mode conversion. Therefore, the resulting signal of even a relatively mode-pure, narrowband excitation in a complex structure is likely to be at least somewhat more complex. With the aforementioned effects, wave propagation and damping and the wave reflection from the structures edges all being mode-dependent and direction dependant, any change to the signal will have a varying relative influence on speed and amplitude of the single wave packages whose overlapping creates the signal itself. These changes therefore can produce local deviations where two different wave packages are overlapping (see Fig. 11).

Fig. 11: Example for local signal deviations due to conditioning.

As this all happens in an undamaged state, false alarms are hard to avoid. Fig. 8 F shows an example for the large influence a short time under hot/wet conditions can have. The problem is complicated by

the even more complex behavior of a complex structure under environmental effects, where, e.g., humidity absorption under a stiffened area will take longer due to the higher local thickness, leading to an even more complex behavior.

At first sight, an adaptive approach does not suffer as much from these constraints. With the waves created by low velocity impacts being predominantly in the low frequency range and only the beginning of the sensors response important for the calculations, the principle behind such an approach is relatively robust. However, there are a multitude of limitations to such a method, too. Firstly, the results can only be as good as the model. On the one hand, as the lowest Lamb wave modes are not (equally) sensitive to changes to all parts of the stiffness tensor, only parts of said tensor are inversely measurable (see [19]). Additionally, the accurateness with which the impact localization occurs can heavily alter the results. The structural model itself quickly becomes very complicated for more complex parts, e.g. curved skin with reinforcements of different orientations and a non-symmetric layup will result in far more complex algorithms, with the additional tolerances and deviations between model and real structure leading to an even larger distribution of the results.

The most important part, however, is the influence of various environmental effects on the wave creation during impact. When actual damage occurs, the relation between contact force and wave generation isn't as straightforward as in the case used for the described approach. Additional compensation methods are required to account for the amount of energy that is lost locally during the impact event and cannot be measured at the sensor position.

4. Impact on SHM and Research Needs

In general, the certification of a SHM system integrated into or attached to a structure will always demand that the SHM system can sustain any operational demands that the structure has to sustain. It (the SHM system) and any damage detection algorithm, as well as any algorithm or method used for compensation of non-damage related effects, should therefore be tested under the same condition as the structure it has to monitor. The approach used has to additionally keep in mind that, for an SHM system, the effects of smaller, but locally varying

changes such as temperature or humidity absorption gradients, might have worse effects than that of large, but global, changes.

In general, one might say that certain effects exist which, in combination with disadvantageous geometries and sensor placement, can lead to uncompensatable signal changes, which are changes that cannot be discerned from actual damage. In addition to ensuring the robustness of a certain SHM system and the compensation methods used in it, the identification of circumstances that might lead to these uncompensatable effects and the development of techniques to prevent their existence is of utmost importance for the transfer from laboratory to real world applications.

This bears the implication that initially, an advanced understanding of all phenomena occurring during the waves interaction with local stiffness discontinuities is necessary to grasp the influence of, e.g., locally non-symmetric properties, the exact configuration of the joint, the angle-dependency of conversion, transmission and reflection and so on. From there, one has to either identify areas where sensor placement is critical or develop methods to limit the influence of these discontinuities. This could for example be done by optimized sensor and actuator placement, optimized excitation strategies (mode tuning [2] etc.), self-restriction of the monitoring objectives (e.g. by using only one-dimensional wave propagation to monitor a critical area) or the optimization of stiffness discontinuities regarding their geometry and their properties (e.g. by varying the layout) to minimize their interaction with the Lamb waves used for monitoring.

The effectiveness of any of these approaches will, just as the compensation methods themselves, have to be verified for all possible conditions and, most importantly, any possible combination of influencing factors to ensure its feasibility. Especially due to the existence of slow factors such as humidity absorption, this means that further developments will have to focus less on baseline methods and more on a combination of baseline-free methods, stochastic approaches and structural and system optimization which allows stretch- and similarity-based methods to work.

5. Conclusions

In this work, the large impact that several factors, namely temperature changes, humidity absorption,

loads and fatigue, have on the sensor response of a surface applied SHM system for an anisotropic composite structure was shown. Composite specific characteristics such as the direction- and mode dependency were shown and their implications for SHM discussed. Especially the existence of slowly changing, locally varying factors such as humidity absorption was identified as a possible hindrance for SHM of complex structures. All factors under investigation were shown to have a significant influence on the Lamb waves, with changes often far in excess of that typically accepted by compensation approaches developed for metallic, isotropic materials (e.g. -40dB).

The requirements that have to be met by a compensation approach able to account for these factors were discussed. For two different compensation methods, the limitations that arise from the combination of issues such as interferences and environmental effects in combination with the composite-specific mode and directional dependency of Lamb wave excitation, propagation and damping were shown. The impact of these effects was shown to result in very large changes to the signal, of comparable and even larger size than that of actual damage introduction.

Due to the large significance of the investigated effects and the unacceptable effort connected to a simple baseline method to account for all possible combinations of said effects, a number of possible methods to reduce the repercussions of these effects was discussed. While some of the composite-specific effects on the Lamb waves behavior might be counteracted using, e.g. optimal sensor positioning, advanced analytical compensation approaches or optimization of stiffness discontinuities, one has to accept that there are a lot more influencing factors in a composite structure when compared to a geometrically identical metallic structure, which implies that the damage detection threshold in a composite structure will hence always be above that achievable in a metallic part.

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful for funding of this work provided by DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft) under grant HE 2574/18-1. Additionally, the support of Mr. Daniel Weigel and Mrs. Manuela von Salzen (both Faserinstitut Bremen e.V.) and Mr. Sascha Diedler and Mr. Robin

Sagurna (both University of Bremen) during some of the experimental parts of this work was gratefully appreciated.

References

- [1] Su, Z., Ye, L.: "Identification of Damage Using Lamb Waves - From Fundamentals to Applications." Springer, 2009.
- [2] Giurgiutiu, V.: "Structural Health Monitoring With Piezoelectric Wafer Active Sensors." Academic Press, 2008.
- [3] Balageas, D., Fritzen, C.-P., Güemes, A.: *Structural Health Monitoring*. ISTE, 2006.
- [4] Rheinforth, M., Kosmann, N., Sauer, D., Busse, G., Schulte, K.: Lamb waves for non-contact fatigue state evaluation of composites under various mechanical loading conditions. *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 43, pp. 1203-1211, 2012.
- [5] Castaings, M., Hosten, B.: "Ultrasonic guided waves for health monitoring of high-pressure composite tanks." *NDT & E International*. Vol. 41, pp 648-655, 2008.
- [6] Castaings, M., Hosten, B., Kundu, T.: Inversion of ultrasonic, plane-wave transmission data in composite plates to infer viscoelastic material properties. *NDT & E International*., Vol. 33, pp. 377-392, 2000.
- [7] Zhao, X., Gao, H., Zhang, G., Ayhan B., Yan F., Kwan, C., Rose, J.: Active health monitoring of an aircraft wing with embedded piezoelectric sensor/actuator network: I. Defect detection, localization and growth monitoring. *Smart Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 16, pp. 1208-1217, 2007.
- [8] Staszewski, W., Mahzan, S., Traynor, R.: Health monitoring of aerospace composite structures – Active and passive approach. *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 69 pp. 1678–1685, 2009.
- [9] Matt, H.M.: *Structural Diagnostics of CFRP Composite Aircraft Components by Ultrasonic Guided Waves and Built-In Piezoelectric Transducers*. University of California, San Diego, 2007.
- [10] Clarke, T., Simonetti, F., Cawley, P.: Guided wave health monitoring of complex structures by sparse array systems: Influence of temperature changes on performance. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol. 329, p.2306-2322, 2010.
- [11] Croxford, A., Moll, J., Wilcox, P., Michaels, J.: "Efficient temperature compensation strategies for guided wave structural health monitoring", *Ultrasonics*, Vol. 50, pp 517-528, 2010.
- [12] Lu, Y., Michaels, J.E.: A methodology for structural health monitoring with diffuse ultrasonic waves in the presence of temperature variations. *Ultrasonics*, Vol. 43 (9), pp.717-731, 2005.
- [13] Sohn, H.: Effects of environmental and operational variability on structural health monitoring, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A*, Vol. 365, pp. 539-560, 2006.
- [14] Lu, Y., Michaels, J.: Feature Extraction and Sensor Fusion for Ultrasonic Structural Health Monitoring Under Changing Environmental Conditions. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, Vol. 9, No.11, pp. 1462-1471, 2009
- [15] Schubert, K., Herrmann, A.: "On the influence of moisture absorption on Lamb wave propagation and measurements in viscoelastic CFRP using surface applied piezoelectric sensors", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 94, pp3635-3643, 2012.
- [16] H.Sohn, C.R.Farrar, F.M.Hemez, D.D.Shunk, D.W.Stinemates and B.R.Nadler, *A Review of Structural Health Monitoring Literature: 1996-2001*. Los Alamos National Laboratory, USA. 2003
- [17] Michaels, J., Michaels, T.: Detection of Structural Damage from the Local Temporal Coherence of Diffuse Ultrasonic Signals. *IEEE Transactions on Ultrasonics, Ferroelectrics, and Frequency Control*, Vol. 52, pp. 1769-1782, 2005.
- [18] Tracy, M., Chang, F.-K.: Identifying Impacts in Composite Plates with piezoelectric Strain Sensors, Part I: Theory, *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, Vol. 9 pp. 920-928, 1998.
- [19] Calomfirescu, M.: *Lamb Waves for Structural Health Monitoring in Viscoelastic Composite Materials*, Logos, 2008.
- [20] Schubert, K., Herrmann, A.: A Compensation Method for Environmental Influences on Passive Lamb Wave Based Impact Evaluation for CFRP. Submitted to: *Key Engineering Materials*.